

An Examination of Sectoral Herding in the French Stock Market

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Abstract

Purpose: This paper aims to detect the presence of herding behavior in the French stock market at the industry level and under several market states. **Methodology:** The authors use closing prices of 270 companies listed on Paris Stock Exchange and pertaining to 9 industries, namely Industrials, Technology, Utilities, Basic Materials, Financials, Consumer Good, Health Care, Oil & Gas and Consumer Services. The study period ranges from January 1, 2017 to October 31, 2022, covering the COVID-19 crisis and the Russia-Ukraine war. The CrossSectional Absolute Deviation of returns (CSAD) model, proposed by Chang, Cheng and Khorana (2000), and the quantile regressions (QR) are used to examine the occurrence of herding behavior in different market states. GARCH model is applied to obtain robust results. **Findings:** The results indicate that herding behavior occurs only in some industries. We report evidence of herding behavior in 2 sectors out of 9 (Technology and Financials). In addition, some market conditions such as downturn, volatility and trading volumes appear to cause the formation of herding behavior. Additionally, investors in some sectors are likely to herd during crisis periods and high uncertainty levels. The results of the quantile regression indicate that herding behavior varies across quantiles. **Originality:** Prior studies on herding behavior have primarily focused on global stock markets, while this behavior may occur within specific

activity sectors. The novelty of this paper lies in examining herding behavior at the industry level and under various market conditions. Also, we conducted a comparative study between the results found by each of the two methods: CSAD and QR. While the CSAD model is useful for detecting aggregate patterns, the quantile regression approach offers a richer and more detailed understanding of herding behavior, especially under extreme market conditions and within specific sectors. **Research implications:** Our findings could aid investors, portfolio managers and policymakers to understand the causes of mispricing in some sectors. The presence of herding in the Technology and Financials sectors implies that policymakers should remove information asymmetry in these two sectors to avoid mispricing and ensure market efficiency. The anti-herding behavior documented in the sectors of Basic materials, Consumer goods and Oil & Gas may be attributed to a good information environment in these sectors. The presence of herding in some sectors and anti-herding in others imply that investors and portfolio managers ought to adopt an effective diversification strategy by spreading their investments across a number of sectors to reduce loss due to herding. This diversification strategy should be revised depending on market conditions since our findings reveal that herding behavior has an asymmetric characteristic. Policymakers are called to monitor the efficiency of the financial market, particularly for some activity sectors.

Keywords: Herding behavior, Sectoral herding, Asymmetric herding, CSAD model, Quantile regressions, COVID-19, Russia-Ukraine war.

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1. Introduction

For several decades following its introduction in the 1960s, the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) formed the cornerstone of numerous financial models, until the emergence of behavioral finance challenged its dominance around thirty years ago (Shleifer, 2000). The EMH posits that financial markets operate efficiently, meaning that asset prices incorporate all existing information. Based on this view, neither individual nor institutional investors could consistently outperform the market using private insights, as any advantage would already be reflected in current prices. Consequently, only unforeseen, new information -by nature random- could drive changes in asset values (Alagidede, 2008). The hypothesis also implies that price movements or returns follow an

independent and identically distributed pattern, aligning with the principles of the random walk theory (Hall, 1978). However, as the 21st century approached, both the theoretical foundations and empirical support for the EMH came under increased scrutiny and debate.

Criticism of the EMH has largely stemmed from its neglect of two key factors: the assumption of investor rationality and the existence of arbitrage opportunities. While EMH assumes that market participants act rationally, behavioral research has shown that investors are influenced by cognitive biases that affect their expectations and choices over time. Additionally, institutional and structural limitations within financial markets can create arbitrage possibilities, allowing certain investors to exploit pricing inefficiencies. As a result, researchers have documented a range of market anomalies that enable some participants to earn above-average returns (Schwert, 2003; Alagidede, 2008). This evidence contradicts the notion that all investors will achieve identical returns through similar strategies. In fact, empirical studies have demonstrated that specific behaviors and strategies, such as herding and momentum investing, can yield abnormal profits (Chang et al., 2000; Jegadeesh & Titman, 2001). In response to these limitations, behavioral finance has emerged as a compelling alternative framework to the EMH. According to Ricciardi and Simon (2000), behavioral finance focuses on understanding the psychological and social factors that influence decision-making at the individual, group, and organizational levels. Gaining insights into investor behavior and its impact on asset prices is therefore essential for a more comprehensive understanding of financial markets.

Behavioral finance finds its origins in the pioneering work of psychologists Kahneman and Tversky in 1979 which lays the foundations of an alternative financial theory in which the psychology interacts with finance to better understand the movements of stock prices. Several studies on behavioral finance concluded that, under given conditions, investors act according to cognitive biases (Fama, 1998; De Bondt et al., 2013). Decision-making biases in the presence of risk, uncertainty or lack of relevant information lead to an increase of market volatility and a difference between the security's market value and its fundamental value (Shiller, 2000). One of the main concepts in behavioral finance that has deserved the attention of academic researchers is herd behavior. Herding is one of the behavioral biases mostly suggested as explaining factors of investor behavior in stock markets (Devenow & Welch, 1996). Herding behavior is widely recognized as the social behavior of ignoring personal information and following the crowd (Bikhchandani et al., 1992). In the behavioral finance literature, herding occurs when investors, who are inclined to buy or sell based on their private information, alter their decisions after observing the market's tendency. Consequently, when investors trade in the same direction, asset prices move away from their fundamental values, leading to excessive market volatility. Numerous studies indicate the occurrence of herding behavior in both developed stock markets (Tan et al. 2008; Mobarek et al., 2014; Economou et al. 2015; Espinosa-Méndez &

Arias, 2021a; Ferreruela et al. 2021; Bogdan et al. 2022; Ampofo et al. 2023) and emerging markets (Chang et al. 2000; Chiang & Zheng, 2010; Batmunkh et al. 2020; Dhall & Singh, 2020; Bougatef & Nejah, 2023). It should be noted that the absence of herding behavior in the entire market does not necessarily deny its presence in certain sectors. Empirical studies have extensively examined sector-specific herd behavior in the US market (Gebka & Wohar, 2013; Litimi et al., 2016; BenSaïda, 2017; Ukpong et al., 2021). In contrast, very few studies empirically investigate sectoral herding in European countries as the case of the French market. Litimi (2017) examines the presence of herding behavior in various French industries. He finds that herding in the French market is prevalent during crises, and it is present during the entire period except in few industries.

The lack of studies on herding behavior in the French market, especially at the sectoral level, inspires us to examine this behavior in different sectors in France rather than in the market as a whole. Thus, we use two econometric methods to detect herding behavior and to assess the impact of external factors (crises and Economic Policy Uncertainty, EPU) on the presence of this behavior among investors in the whole French market and in its different sectors : The Cross-Sectional Absolute Deviation of returns (CSAD) model, proposed by Chang, Cheng and Khorana (2000), and the quantile regressions (QR). We conduct a comparative analysis of the results provided by these methods. Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (GARCH) model is applied to obtain robust results.

Our study contributes to the literature in three ways. First, it extends the scarce literature on sectoral herding in European stock markets. Second, we extend the study of Litimi (2017) on industry herding in French stock market through investigating the occurrence of such behavior during the two most recent crisis periods, namely the COVID-19 pandemic and the RussiaUkraine war. Third, we examine the potential effects of the EPU on herd behavior and identify some external factors that may contribute to stock market investors' tendency to follow the herd. Our findings indicate the absence of herding behavior in the entire market over the whole study period. Regarding the industry level, herding behavior is present in 2 sectors out of 9 (Technology and Financials), while 3 sectors (Basic materials, Consumer goods and Oil & Gas) exhibit an anti-herding behavior. We also point out that these herding and anti-herding behaviors have an asymmetric characteristic. Also, we conducted a comparative study between the results found by each of the two methods: CSAD and QR. While the CSAD model is useful for detecting aggregate patterns, the quantile regression approach offers a richer and more detailed understanding of herding behavior, especially under extreme market conditions and within specific sectors.

The rest of the paper is presented as follows. **Section 2** provides the literature review on herd behavior and develops hypotheses. **Section 3** describes the data and methodology. **Section 4** presents

and discusses the results. **Section 5** checks the robustness of these results. Finally, **Section 6** concludes the article.

2. Literature review and hypotheses development

Abundant studies have attempted to detect herding behavior among investors in various stock markets. However, there is no consensus on its presence since empirical results are mixed. Christie and Huang (1995) pioneered the studies on herd behavior in the US stock market, but their findings did not report any evidence on the presence of such behavior neither for daily data nor for monthly data. Using the CSAD model, Chang et al. (2000) examine herding behavior on different international markets (the United States; Hong Kong; Japan; South Korea and Taiwan). The study's results indicate that developed and integrated markets did not exhibit herding behavior (the US, Hong Kong, and Japan). However, herding is observed in emerging markets (South Korea and Taiwan). Caparrelli et al. (2004) investigate herding behavior in the Italian stock market and find that herding behavior is present under extreme market conditions. Using the CSAD and CSSD (Cross-Sectional Standard Deviation) models, Economou et al. (2015) examine the effect of joining in a stock market group on herd dynamics. The authors provide evidence on the significance of herd behavior in the three stock markets (Belgium, France and the Netherlands) following their merger into Euronext, while herd behavior in Portugal was present both before and after the merger. Using the CSSD model, Demirer and Kutan (2006) document no evidence on the presence of herding behavior in Chinese markets for both individual firm and sector data. Litimi (2017) finds that herding behavior is absent in the entire French market but is present in 5 sectors out of 11. Building on the results of Litimi (2017), the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H₁: *Herding behavior arises in the French stock market for the entire sample period only at the industry level.*

The existing literature provides empirical evidence that herding behavior is asymmetric but generally more prevalent under challenging market conditions. Tan et al. (2008) examine the herding behavior of Chinese A and B stocks over the period from July 12, 1994 to December 31, 2003. They point out that herd behavior occurs in both rising and falling market conditions. A-share investors in the Shanghai market exhibit more herding behavior in periods of rising markets, high trading volume and high volatility, while no asymmetry was observed for the Bshare market. Using a sample of 18 countries around the world, Chiang and Zheng (2010) find that herding behavior is more likely to occur in advanced (except the US) and Asian markets, especially during downturns, and no evidence

is found on its presence in Latin American countries. Moreover, they document that this behavior is more evident in crisis periods. Demirer et al. (2010) employ the CSAD and CSSD tests, and state space-based models of Hwang and Salmon (2004) and find that the gregarious behavior is present mainly during bear market days in the Taiwanese context, considering both the market as a whole and each sector separately. Mobarek et al. (2014) find that herding behavior in European developed stock markets is not obvious in normal times but prevalent in extreme market conditions. Economou et al. (2018) investigate herding behavior in three developed markets, namely, the United States, the United Kingdom and Germany over the period from January 2004 to July 2014. Their findings provide no evidence of herding on the three stock markets studied, regardless of market conditions (ups or downs). Using the CSAD and the quantile regression method, Choi and Yoon (2020) examine the herd behavior in the Korean stock market (KOSPI and KOSDAQ) over the period from January 2003 to December 2018. They point out that herding exists in both the KOSPI and KOSDAQ markets during market downturns, periods of low trading volume and low volatility. In addition, they conclude that investor sentiment turns out to be one of the important factors that can lead to herding behavior in the Korean stock market.

While a substantial body of research has examined herding behavior across global market indices, relatively limited attention has been paid to industry-specific herding. Litimi et al. (2016), for instance, explore herding across various U.S. sectors and find evidence of such behavior in six out of twelve industries -namely Consumer Non-Durables, Energy, Healthcare, Utilities, Technology, and Transportation- particularly during periods of market turmoil. Employing the CSAD model alongside quantile regression, Duygun et al. (2021) investigate herding in key financial sectors of the U.S. and Eurozone equity markets. Their analysis reveals that herding tends to occur in upper quantiles, typically associated with volatile market conditions, and is more pronounced during financial crises and under asymmetric states of volatility, deteriorating credit conditions, and limited liquidity. Ukpong et al. (2021), using daily data from 1990 to 2020, argue that while herding is not evident at the aggregate U.S. market level, it does exist within specific industries. Camara (2017) examines four major U.S. industries and identifies herding behavior in the manufacturing sector during bull markets and in the service sector during bear markets. In the French context, Litimi (2017) analyzes the effect of herding on conditional idiosyncratic volatility at the industry level, noting that herding is prominent during crisis periods and persistent in only a few sectors throughout the entire observation window. Focusing on nine Asian markets, Zheng et al. (2017) find strong herding in the technology and financial sectors, but comparatively weaker evidence in public utilities. They also observe that herding is generally more intense during market downturns and when trading volumes are low. More recently, Mishra and Mishra (2023) apply quantile regression to study herding among 54 banking and financial

services stocks in India. Their findings indicate herding behavior among public sector institutions, particularly during bullish phases of the pandemic period, within the 90th quantile of return distributions. Drawing on these findings concerning asymmetric herding behavior, we propose the following hypothesis:

H₂ : *Sectoral herding in the French stock market has an asymmetric characteristic.*

This general hypothesis can be divided into the following three sub-hypotheses:

H_{2a} : *Sectoral herd behavior is expected to be more pronounced in bearish market.*

H_{2b} : *Sectoral herd behavior is expected to be positively associated with trading volume.*

H_{2c} : *Sectoral herd behavior is more likely to occur during high volatility periods.* In recent years, several studies have investigated herding behavior in financial markets during periods of pandemic and financial crisis (Espinosa-Méndez & Arias, 2021a,b; Ferreruella & Mallor, 2021). The onset of the COVID-19 pandemic introduced significant uncertainty and heightened investor anxiety, conditions which are conducive to the emergence of herding behavior. Chang et al. (2020) analyze herding in the energy stock markets across the U.S., Europe, and Asia during the periods of the Global Financial Crisis (GFC), SARS (SARSCoV2), and COVID-19. Their findings indicate that herding intensifies in times of extremely low oil returns, and although it was notable following the GFC, it did not significantly emerge during the COVID-19 outbreak. Wu et al. (2020) find that in the Chinese stock markets, herding behavior is more evident during market upswings, when trading volumes are lower, and when volatility declines due to COVID-19. Espinosa-Méndez and Arias (2021a) explore five major European stock markets -France, Germany, Italy, the UK, and Spain- over the period from January 3, 2000, to June 19, 2020. Their results suggest that the pandemic prompted uninformed investors to abandon their own judgments in favor of mimicking more informed players, driven by heightened fear and market uncertainty. Comparable patterns were observed in the Australian stock market (Espinosa-Méndez & Arias, 2021b). Nguyen et al. (2023) apply the CSAD model and quantile regression to investigate herding in the Vietnamese market from January 2016 to May 2022. They report that herding is less prevalent during bullish phases but becomes more prominent under other market conditions, particularly during the fourth wave of COVID-19. Ampofo et al. (2023) examine how COVID-19 influenced herding behavior in the developed markets of the U.S. and the UK from January 9, 2018, to February 28, 2022. Their analysis, also based on CSAD and quantile regression, reveals herding behavior in both countries during bullish conditions throughout the pandemic, while in bearish conditions, herding was only observed in the U.S. during the COVID-19 period.

Ghorbel et al. (2022) test for the presence of herding behavior among stock indices of developed and BRICS countries during the COVID-19 crisis, using a modified CSAD measure and wavelet coherence (WC) analysis. Their results show that the herding was present during all four waves of COVID-19 and was boosted by trading volume and the number of deaths. Furthermore, the results of the wavelet coherence analysis indicate the presence of herding behavior between China and developed and emerging stock markets, particularly during the first wave of the crisis, and between Indian and stock markets, particularly during the third wave of the COVID-19 crisis. Viona et al. (2023) use the static CSAD model and the sliding window approach to examine sectoral herding behavior in the Indonesian stock market during the Covid 19 pandemic. Their results from the CSAD model reveal no evidence of herding, while the results from the rolling-window approach show significant herd behavior. Using the CSAD model, Enow (2023) investigates the presence of herd behavior in the South African stock market during the Covid 19 pandemic. He finds evidence of a herd attitude during the pandemic period. Roy et al. (2023) examine the sectoral presence of persistent volatility and herding behavior in 7 identical sectors in Australia and New Zealand, both before and after the COVID-19 pandemic. Using the GARCH methods for the analysis of volatility and the CSAD approach, the authors document the existence of herding behavior only in the sector of discretionary consumption for both countries.

Similar to the COVID-19 pandemic, the instability and heightened uncertainty triggered by the Russian invasion are anticipated to influence investor behavior. Analyzing daily closing prices of stocks listed on the MOEX Russia Index from June 16, 2021, to November 30, 2022, Bougatef and Nejah (2023) find that the Russia-Ukraine conflict contributed to the emergence of herding behavior among investors on the Moscow Exchange. However, their findings indicate that such behavior is confined to periods of market decline. Given the inconclusive and mixed findings from the few studies on financial markets, we contribute to this area by examining whether investors in the French stock market exhibit a sectoral herding behavior during the two recent crisis periods, namely the Covid 19 pandemic and the Russian-Ukrainian war. Thus, we formulate the following hypothesis:

H3: *Industry herding is more pronounced during the COVID-19 period and the Russia-Ukraine war.*

Some other studies argue that herd behavior occurs due to specific phenomena linked to various market anomalies, such as uncertainty, investor sentiment. Economou et al. (2018) explore the relationship between the Volatility Index (VIX) and herding of stocks in the United States, the United Kingdom and Germany. They document the statistically significant impact of fear on herding estimations. Using daily data from July 16, 2011 to August 4, 2022 of stock-listed companies in Saudi

Arabia and the US EPU index as a proxy for uncertainty, Altamimi et al. (2023) report significant evidence of anti-herding behavior in the low uncertainty state and significant evidence of herding behavior in the normal and high uncertainty states. Using data for portfolios categorized by size, Aharon (2021) examines the relationship between market sentiment, as measured by the CBOE Volatility Index, the VIX, and the herding phenomenon in the US market. He finds that the VIX has a substantial impact on herding behavior in all groups and subgroups of portfolios. Bouri et al. (2019) provide evidence that herding behavior in the cryptocurrency market intensifies as uncertainty, measured by the U.S. Economic Policy Uncertainty (EPU) index, rises. However, using the CSAD model and time-varying Markovswitching (TV-MS), Coskun et al. (2020) argue that anti-herding occurs when the uncertainty expressed by the US EPU increases. Youssef (2022) shows that investors are more likely to imitate their peers when volatility, the S&P500 and the dollar index increase. However, increases in trading volume, gold prices, and the Economic Policy Uncertainty Index (EPU) are reducing herding behavior in the cryptocurrency market. Given that the majority of previous studies have documented positive association between uncertainty and herding behavior, we formulate the following hypothesis:

H₄: *Sectoral herd behavior in the French stock market is more prevalent during high uncertainty periods.*

Table 1 summarizes the hypotheses to be tested in this study and their empirical underpinnings. As can be shown, there is an increasing number of studies on the effect of COVID-19 on herding behavior, while only one study is found on Russia-Ukraine war. Thus, this study will extend the existing literature on the contribution of crises to the formation of herding behavior. Unlike the majority of previous works, this study will investigate the effect of these two crises on herding behaviour at the industry level. Indeed, the only study on sectoral herding during the COVID-19 period is that of Mishra and Mishra (2023) who examine the effect of this health crisis on herding behavior in banking and financial services. In addition, there is no study to date has explored explores whether sectoral herding arises in response to economic policy uncertainty (EPU). Thus, this study aims to fill this research gap.

Table 1. Summary of empirical evidences on herding behavior.

Market conditions		Previous empirical studies	Hypotheses
Market state	Bearish	Caparrelli et al. (2004) ; Tan et al., (2008) ; Demirer et al., (2010) ; Chiang and Zheng (2010) ; Mobarek et al., (2014) ; Camara et al., (2017) ; Zheng et al., (2017) ; Choi and Yoon (2020) ; Espinosa-Méndez and Arias (2021b) ; Nguyen et al. (2023) ; Bougatef and Nejah (2023) ; Ampofo et al., (2023)	H2a
	Bullish	Caparrelli et al. (2004) ; Tan et al., (2008) ; Chiang and Zheng (2010) ; Arjoon and Bhatnagar (2017) ; Camara et al., (2017) ; Wu et al., (2020) ; Espinosa-Méndez and Arias (2021b) ; Mishra and Mishra (2023)	
Trading volume	High	Tan et al., (2008) ; Mobarek et al., (2014) ; Zheng et al., (2017) ; Espinosa-Méndez and Arias (2021b) ; Ghorbel et al., (2022) ; Nguyen et al. (2023)	H2b
	Low	Mobarek et al., (2014) ; Choi and Yoon (2020) ; Wu et al., (2020) ; Youssef (2022) ; Nguyen et al. (2023)	
Volatility	High	Tan et al., (2008) ; Gavriilidis et al., 2013 ; Mobarek et al., (2014) ; Espinosa-Méndez and Arias (2021b)	H2c
	Low	Mobarek et al., (2014); Choi and Yoon (2020); Wu et al., (2020)	
Crisis	COVID- 19	Espinosa-Méndez and Arias (2021a) ; Espinosa-Méndez and Arias (2021b) ; Bouri et al., (2021) ; Ghorbel et al., (2022) ; Nguyen et al. (2023) ; Ampofo et al., (2023) ; Viona et al., (2023) ; Mishra and Mishra (2023)	H3
	Russia-	Bougatef and Nejah (2023)	H3
	Ukraine war		
EPU		Bouri et al., (2019) ; Altamimi et al. (2023)	H4

Source : Authors' Contribution.

3. Data and methodology

3.1. Data

The data used to investigate herding behavior in the French stock market consists of closing prices of 270 companies listed on Paris Stock Exchange and pertaining to 9 industries, namely Industrials, Technology, Utilities, Basic Materials, Financials, Consumer Good, Health Care, Oil & Gas and Consumer Services. The study period ranges from January 1, 2017 to October 31, 2022; which gives 1521 daily observations for each company. This study period is chosen because it covers two major crises: The COVID-19 crisis (January 1, 2020-July 31, 2020) and the Russian-Ukraine conflict (February 24, 2022-October 31, 2022). These two crises are suggested by prior studies as responsible for the occurrence of herding behavior. The period of the COVID-19 pandemic is determined following Choi (2021), while that of the Russia-Ukraine conflict is determined following Boungou

and Yatié (2022). Daily returns are calculated as the natural logarithm of the closing price of the stock i on day t divided by its closing price on the previous trading day: $R_{i,t} = \ln(P_t/P_{t-1})$. Stock prices and trading volumes are collected from www.investing.com, while the EPU index, constructed by Baker et al. (2016), is available on the website (www.policyuncertainty.com).

3.2. Methodology

3.2.1. The Cross-Sectional Absolute Deviation of returns (CSAD) model, proposed by Chang, Cheng and Khorana (2000)

The literature suggests that there are two widely used measures to detect herd behavior in stock markets. Christie and Huang (1995) proposed the CSSD approach which states that the investment decision process followed by market participants depends on general market conditions. They argue that during normal times, rational asset pricing models predict that the dispersion of returns will increase with the absolute value of market return, since individual investors trading is based on their own private information. In contrast, during times of extreme market movements, individuals tend to ignore their own beliefs, and their investment decisions are more likely to follow those of other investors. Consequently, individual stock returns under these conditions should tend to cluster around the overall market return. However, several researchers (Hwang & Salmon 2004; Chiang & Zheng 2010; Economou et al. 2011) have reported that the CSSD measure is sensitive to outliers. Accordingly, Chang et al. (2000) proposed an alternative measure of the dispersion of returns, the CSAD, computed as:

$$CSAD_t = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |R_{i,t} - R_{m,t}| \quad (1)$$

Where $R_{i,t}$ is the observed return of stock i at time t , $R_{m,t}$ is the equal-weighted average return of the N stocks that constitute the sectorial index at time t . To detect herd behavior, Chang et al. (2000) proposed the following regression based on a general quadratic relationship:

$$CSAD_t = \alpha + \gamma_1 |R_{m,t}| + \gamma_2 R_{m,t}^2 + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

The term $R_{m,t}^2$ is used to capture the herd behavior of investors. γ_1 and γ_2 are coefficients and ε_t refers to error terms. Accordingly, a negative and statistically significant parameter γ_2 indicates the presence of herding behavior.

A number of empirical studies have found evidence of asymmetric herding behavior under different market conditions (Chang et al., 2000; Chiang & Zheng, 2010; Economou et al., 2011; Mobarek et al., 2014).

Bullish or Bearish Market

The asymmetric effects of stock returns on the formation of herding behavior have been documented by a large body of the existing literature. Arjoon and Bhatnagar (2017) point out that herding behavior was more pronounced in rising markets, while Chang et al., (2000); Chiang and Zheng, (2010) and Mobarek et al. (2014) find that it was more prevalent in falling markets. To test for herding behavior asymmetry, we follow the approach of Chiang and Zheng (2010), who use a dummy variable approach in a single model, which is found to be more reliable than that of Tan et al. (2008). Thus, we estimate the following equation:

$$CSAD_t = \alpha + \gamma_1 Dup|R_{m,t}| + \gamma_2(1 - Dup)|R_{m,t}| + \gamma_3 Dup(R_{m,t})^2 + \gamma_4(1 - Dup)(R_{m,t})^2 + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

where Dup is a dummy variable that takes the value 1 if the average market return on day t is positive and 0 otherwise. Negative estimates of coefficients γ_3 and γ_4 reflect the presence of asymmetric herding behavior in bull and bear markets, respectively.

High or Low Volume

Trading volume has been suggested as one of the indicators of investor sentiment (Baker & Stein, 2004; Kumar & Lee, 2006) and is used as a measure of herding behavior in financial markets (Lakonishok et al. 1992; Sias, 2004). Therefore, trading volume may be one of the factors that lead to the presence of herding behavior. To examine the asymmetric effects of high and low trading volumes on herding behavior, we estimate the following equation:

$$CSAD_t = \alpha + \gamma_1 D^{Vol-high}|R_{m,t}| + \gamma_2(1 - D^{Vol-high})|R_{m,t}| + \gamma_3 D^{Vol-high}(R_{m,t})^2 + \gamma_4(1 - D^{Vol-high})(R_{m,t})^2 + \varepsilon_t \quad (4)$$

Where $D^{Vol-high}$ is a dummy variable that takes the value 1 on days characterized by high trading volume and 0 otherwise. Following Tan et al. (2008), we characterize the trading volume as high on day t if it exceeds the previous 30-day moving average. If herding behavior is more pronounced on days of high trading volume, γ_3 is expected to be less than γ_4 .

High or Low Volatility

Numerous studies (Economou et al., 2011; Holmes et al., 2013; Guney et al., 2017) suggest that the tendency to imitate is more pronounced during periods of low volatility. Indeed, lower volatility makes it easier for investors to observe the actions of their peers and therefore imitate them. On the other hand, a high level of volatility can also promote herding behavior in financial markets (Gleason et al., 2004; Tan et al., 2008; Gavriilidis et al., 2013), if the volatility is the result of an increase in the flow of information; in this case, uninformed investors can follow the actions of their informed peers in order to benefit from their information for free. A high level of volatility in the financial market can

also induce herding due to the high degree of uncertainty it involves (the market environment becomes more complex), thus encouraging investors to imitate their peers in order to reduce this uncertainty (Economou et al., 2015). Market volatility is calculated as the squared market return, in line with the studies of Economou et al. (2011) and Tan et al. (2008). We use the following equation to examine the asymmetric effects of volatility:

$$CSAD_t = \alpha + \gamma_1 D^{\sigma^2\text{-high}} |R_{m,t}| + \gamma_2 (1 - D^{\sigma^2\text{-high}}) |R_{m,t}| + \gamma_3 D^{\sigma^2\text{-high}} (R_{m,t})^2 + \gamma_4 (1 - D^{\sigma^2\text{-high}}) (R_{m,t})^2 + \varepsilon_t \quad (5)$$

Where $D^{\sigma^2\text{-high}}$ is a dummy variable that takes the value 1 on days characterized by high volatility and 0 otherwise. Volatility is defined as high (low) if it is above (below) the previous 30-day moving average.

Herding Behavior and Crisis Periods

The global COVID-19 pandemic has had a devastating impact on all global economies, deeply affecting both the real and financial sectors. More specifically, this health crisis has disrupted health systems, supply chains, business activities and investments, generating a series of panic attacks and uncertainty among market participants, which has significantly complicated the investment decision-making. In this context, numerous studies have been carried out to explore the possibility of herd behavior in financial markets (Dhall & Singh, 2020; Espinosa-Méndez & Arias, 2021a; Bouri et al., 2021; Bougateg & Nejah, 2023) who found a direct link between the COVID-19 pandemic and herd formation among market participants in global financial markets. Thus, we use the following equation to analyze the effects of the two crises, namely the COVID-19 pandemic and the Russia-Ukraine war, on the formation of herd behavior in the French stock market at the industry level:

$$CSAD_t = \alpha + \gamma_1 |R_{m,t}| + \gamma_2 R_{m,t}^2 + \gamma_3 D^{\text{crisis}} R_{m,t}^2 + \varepsilon_t \quad (6)$$

D^{crisis} is a dummy variable which highlights the crisis period and takes the value 1 during the period characterized by a crisis event and 0 otherwise. The period of the COVID-19 pandemic crisis (January 1, 2020-July 31, 2020) is determined following Choi (2021), while that of the Russia-Ukraine conflict (February 24, 2022 - October 31, 2022) is determined following Boungou and Yatié (2022). Investors tend to herd during both crises if γ_3 is significantly negative.

Herding Behavior and Economic Policy Uncertainty

To capture herding in periods of low and high economic policy uncertainty (EPU), we use the following regression equation:

$$CSAD_t = \alpha + \gamma_1 D^{\text{highEPU}} |R_{m,t}| + \gamma_2 (1 - D^{\text{highEPU}}) |R_{m,t}| + \gamma_3 D^{\text{highEPU}} (R_{m,t})^2 + \gamma_4 (1 - D^{\text{highEPU}}) (R_{m,t})^2 + \varepsilon_t \quad (7)$$

Where EPU represents the investor sentiment and the degree of uncertainty. $D^{highEPU} = 1$ if EPU is above its median value.

3.2.2. The Quantile Regressions (QR)

In order to strengthen the reliability of our study, we adopt a more advanced approach using a quantile method. The QR model is a statistical method usually used in extreme value analysis, and it expresses a dependent variable as a function of explanatory variables. Compared to a traditional regression model, QR functions provide a more precise result of the impact of conditional variables on the dependent variable (Koenker, 2005). Therefore, equation (2) is transformed into a QR model as:

$$Q_{\tau}(\tau Y_t) = \alpha_{\tau} + \gamma_{1,\tau}|R_{m,t}| + \gamma_{2,\tau}R_{m,t}^2 + \varepsilon_{t,\tau} \quad (8)$$

where Y_t denotes the vector of regressors mentioned to the right of the aforementioned equation. A significant and negative value of coefficient $\gamma_{2,\tau}$ indicates the presence of industry herding for the quantile τ .

Similarly, equation (3) is reformulated as follows:

$$Q_{\tau}(\tau Y_t) = \alpha + \gamma_{1,\tau}Dup|R_{m,t}| + \gamma_{2,\tau}(1 - Dup)|R_{m,t}| + \gamma_{3,\tau}Dup(R_{m,t})^2 + \gamma_{4,\tau}(1 - Dup)(R_{m,t})^2 + \varepsilon_{t,\tau} \quad (9)$$

Significantly negative values of $\gamma_{3,\tau}$ and $\gamma_{4,\tau}$ suggest the occurrence of herding behavior during the bull ($R_{m,t} > 0$) and bear ($R_{m,t} < 0$) market states, respectively.

The equation (4) is transformed into a QR model as follows:

$$Q_{\tau}(\tau Y_t) = \alpha + \gamma_{1,\tau}DVol-high|R_{m,t}| + \gamma_{2,\tau}(1 - DVol-high)|R_{m,t}| + \gamma_{3,\tau}DVol-high(R_{m,t})^2 + \gamma_{4,\tau}(1 - DVol-high)(R_{m,t})^2 + \varepsilon_{t,\tau} \quad (10)$$

Statistically significant and negative coefficients $\gamma_{3,\tau}$ and $\gamma_{4,\tau}$ highlight quantile-specific sector herding behavior in periods of high and low trading volumes, respectively.

The equation (5) is transformed into a QR model as follows:

$$Q_{\tau}(\tau Y_t) = \alpha + \gamma_{1,\tau}D\sigma^2-high|R_{m,t}| + \gamma_{2,\tau}(1 - D\sigma^2-high)|R_{m,t}| + \gamma_{3,\tau}D\sigma^2-high(R_{m,t})^2 + \gamma_{4,\tau}(1 - D\sigma^2-high)(R_{m,t})^2 + \varepsilon_{t,\tau} \quad (11)$$

Statistically significant and negative coefficients $\gamma_{3,\tau}$ and $\gamma_{4,\tau}$ respectively exhibit quantilespecific sectoral herding behavior in periods of high and low market volatility, respectively.

The equation (6) is transformed into a QR model as follows:

$$Q_{\tau}(\tau Y_t) = \alpha + \gamma_{1,\tau}|R_{m,t}| + \gamma_{2,\tau}R_{m,t}^2 + \gamma_{3,\tau}D^{crisis}R_{m,t}^2 + \varepsilon_t \quad (12)$$

A significantly negative coefficient $\gamma_{3,\tau}$ suggests a strong herding behavior during the two crisis periods, namely, the Covid 19 pandemic and the Russian-Ukraine conflict.

The equation (7) is transformed into a QR model as follows:

$$Q\tau(\tau Y_t) = \alpha + \gamma_{1,\tau} D^{highEPU} |R_{m,t}| + \gamma_{2,\tau} (1 - D^{highEPU}) |R_{m,t}| + \gamma_{3,\tau} D^{highEPU} (R_{m,t})^2 + \gamma_{4,\tau} (1 - D^{highEPU}) (R_{m,t})^2 + \varepsilon_t \quad (13)$$

Statistically significant and negative coefficients $\gamma_{3,\tau}$ and $\gamma_{4,\tau}$ respectively exhibit quantilespecific sectoral herding behavior in periods of high and low economic policy uncertainty (EPU), respectively.

4. Empirical Results and Discussions

4.1. Results of CSAD Model

4.1.1. Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 displays the descriptive statistics for the average daily returns R_m and the CSAD across different industries. Over the analysis period, the Utilities sector recorded the highest average return (2.18E-4), whereas the Health Care sector exhibited the lowest average daily return (-

6.29E-04). The Basic Materials sector experienced the greatest standard deviation (0.014), indicating significant volatility. Furthermore, the Jarque-Bera test rejects the assumption of normality for all sectors analyzed. It is also evident that CSAD values vary among sectors, with the Health Care and Oil & Gas sectors showing comparatively higher levels. The skewness coefficients confirm the deviation from normal distribution for all variables. According to **Table 2**, the daily return distributions for all industries are negatively skewed, as shown by their negative skewness values. Conversely, all CSAD values are positive, suggesting asymmetry and a right-skewed distribution for this variable. Additionally, all return series exhibit kurtosis values exceeding 3, indicating leptokurtic behavior and the presence of fat tails in the distributions. The Jarque-Bera test consistently rejects the null hypothesis of normality for all variables considered. Moving to **Table 3**, the results verify that all data series are stationary based on various statistical tests. To assess stationarity, we applied two versions of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test: one including a constant and another incorporating both a constant and a linear trend. We also used the Phillips-Perron (PP) test under a similar framework. All tests yielded consistent results, confirming the stationarity of the series.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for CSAD and return series by industry.

Industries	Firms	Variables	Mean.	<u>Min. Max. Std.dev.</u>			Skew.	Kurt.	J-B Stat.
All	270	Rm	-1.70E-04	-0.100	0.049	0.009	-1.931	24.217	28892.67***
		CSAD	0.015	0.007	0.061	0.005	3.287	22.024	25169.54***
Industrials	60	Rm	-4.64E-05	-0.112	0.067	0.010	-1.794	26.346	33776.43***
		CSAD	0.013	0.006	0.077	0.006	4.774	40.049	88620.98***
Technology	31	Rm	1.82E-04	-0.103	0.055	0.011	-1.711	17.237	12980.56***
		CSAD	0.015	0.005	0.077	0.005	2.777	23.851	28188.41***
Utilities	11	Rm	2.18E-04	-0.095	0.043	0.009	-1.068	13.750	7272.451***
		CSAD	0.014	0.002	0.075	0.007	2.483	14.738	9834.750***
Basic Materials	14	Rm	-2.44E-04	-0.125	0.070	0.014	-1.179	13.015	6408.877***
		CSAD	0.015	0.004	0.141	0.008	4.342	45.803	115483.1***
Financials	33	Rm	-1.99E-05	-0.100	0.054	0.008	-2.420	38.455	77521.59***
		CSAD	0.010	0.004	0.054	0.005	3.285	21.205	22677.78***
Consumer Good	56	Rm	-2.09E-04	-0.097	0.080	0.010	-0.792	17.284	12608.46***
		CSAD	0.015	0.006	0.163	0.007	9.159	182.513	198755.3***
Health Care	40	Rm	-6.29E-04	-0.102	0.061	0.011	-1.026	12.160	5334.806***
		CSAD	0.019	0.007	0.112	0.008	3.238	24.079	29438.10***
Oil & Gas	8	Rm	1.47E-04	-0.087	0.072	0.013	-0.427	8.732	2032.902***
		CSAD	0.018	0.003	0.138	0.010	2.790	20.882	21244.56***
Consumer Services	17	Rm	-2.228E-05	-0.062	0.032	0.007	-0.588	9.953	3010.440***
		CSAD	0.012	0.003	0.053	0.005	2.390	13.374	7898.726***

Note: Rm refers to the average daily returns of the portfolio composed of all companies in each sector m. *** indicates statistical significance at the 1% level.

Table 3. Results of the unit root tests.

Industries	Variables	With intercept	<u>ADF</u>		<u>PP</u>	
			With intercept & trend	With intercept	With intercept & trend	With intercept & trend
All	Rm	-20.520***	-20.521***	-33.144***	-33.130***	
	CSAD	-6.139***	-6.551***	-17.887***	-19.449***	
Industrial	Rm	-21.428***	-21.421***	-33.531***	-33.522***	
	CSAD	-7.643***	-7.976***	-26.001***	-26.722***	
Technology	Rm	-21.839***	-21.868***	-34.716***	-34.707***	
	CSAD	-11.407***	-11.609***	-35.225***	-34.960***	
Utilities	Rm	-22.937***	-22.929***	-34.806***	-34.796***	
	CSAD	-9.657***	-10.430***	-35.717***	-36.002***	

Basic Materials	Rm	-23.896***	-23.888***	-36.512***	-36.502***
	CSAD	-8.836***	-9.405***	-37.044***	-36.455***
Financials	Rm	-21.450***	-21.490***	-35.206***	-35.171***
	CSAD	-5.421***	-5.834***	-29.343***	-31.221***
Consumer Good	Rm	-22.773***	-22.787***	-33.939***	-33.909***
	CSAD	-6.697***	-7.141***	-35.918***	-35.991***
Health Care	Rm	-20.556***	-20.559***	-30.618***	-30.617***
	CSAD	-8.694***	-9.533***	-36.425***	-36.665***
Oil Gas	Rm	-18.652***	-18.661***	-31.976***	-31.961***
	CSAD	-9.460***	-10.207***	-37.839***	-37.391***
Consumer Services	Rm	-33.602***	-33.594***	-33.813***	-33.804***
	CSAD	-10.679***	-10.812***	-30.924***	-30.945***

Note: *** indicates significance at the 1% significance level.

4.1.2. Herding behavior under several market conditions

Table 4 reports the regression results of equation (2). It shows that the coefficients γ_1 for all the sectors are positive and highly significant, inducing a positive linear relationship between returns $|R_{mt}|$ and the CSAD as stated by the CAPM. For the entire market, the coefficient γ_2 is negative but statistically non-significant indicating the absence of any herd effect on the French market. This finding implies that French investors make rational investment decisions using their own beliefs, personal information and investment strategies instead of following market consensus. These results are consistent with previous evidence from Mobarek et al. (2014) and Galariotis et al. (2016) who used the CSAD model and found no evidence of herding on the French market. However, these results contradict previous findings by Chiang and Zheng (2010) and Ghorbel et al. (2022). In contrast, the coefficients γ_2 are negative and statistically significant for the sectors of Technology and Financials, indicating the presence of herd behavior in these two sectors. Therefore, **H₁** is accepted during the entire sample period. The results of our study are consistent with Litimi (2017) who provides evidence of herding behavior in the Financial sector. The coefficient γ_2 is significantly positive for the sectors of Basic Materials, Consumer Goods and Oil & Gas suggesting the existence of an anti-herding behavior. The plausible explanation of this result is that investors among these 3 sectors are more confident in their own ability and choices (Wang et al. 2017).

Table 4. Industry herding behaviour over the whole sample period.

Industries	α	γ_1	γ_2	Adj. R^2
All	0.012*** (0.000)	0.530*** (0.000)	-0.406 (0.318)	0.5014*** (0.000)
Industrials	0.010*** (0.000)	0.538*** (0.000)	-0.554 (0.120)	0.4739*** (0.000)
Technology	0.012*** (0.000)	0.417*** (0.000)	-1.153*** (0.006)	0.3123*** (0.000)
Utilities	0.009*** (0.000)	0.627*** (0.000)	0.996 (0.180)	0.3953*** (0.000)
Basic Materials	0.011*** (0.000)	0.411*** (0.000)	2.032*** (0.000)	0.3872*** (0.000)
Financials	0.007*** (0.000)	0.718*** (0.000)	-1.954*** (0.000)	0.5990*** (0.000)
Consumer Goods	0.012*** (0.000)	0.321*** (0.000)	5.232*** (0.000)	0.4739*** (0.000)
Health Care	0.015*** (0.000)	0.624*** (0.000)	0.683 (0.349)	0.3971*** (0.000)
Oil & Gas	0.013*** (0.000)	0.435*** (0.000)	4.700*** (0.000)	0.3371*** (0.000)
Consumer Services	0.009*** (0.000)	0.542*** (0.000)	2.369 (0.095)	0.3096*** (0.000)

Notes: *** indicates significance at 1%. P-values are reported in parentheses.

Table 5 shows the results of herding behavior during bull and bear markets. The coefficients γ_3 and γ_4 represent respectively the coefficients of the upward and downward market conditions. The results reveal that, for the entire French stock market, the coefficient γ_3 is positive and statistically significant, indicating that there is no evidence of herding in rising market conditions. Similarly, in declining market conditions, the coefficient γ_4 is negative and statistically non-significant, indicating the absence of herd behavior. Therefore, herding behavior on the entire French market does not depend on market return movements. Our results corroborate previous findings in Chiang and Zheng (2010), Mobarek et al. (2014).

At the industry level, the coefficients γ_4 are negative and statistically significant for the Technology and Financials sectors, suggesting that investors in these sectors tend to herd during

market downturns. This evidence indicates that investors in these sectors are more sensitive to loss during bearish market than to gain during bullish market (Batmunkh et al., 2020). Thus, investors in these two sectors have a greater tendency to protect their loss by moving closer to the market consensus. These results are consistent with Kahneman and Tversky's (1986) prospect theory, which describes investors' asymmetric reactions to gains and losses. Additionally, they support Epstein and Schneider's (2008) perspective that investors are much more sensitive to bad news than to good news. Consequently, H_{2a} is accepted during bearish phases. This result is consistent with previous literature which demonstrates that herding behavior is more pronounced during market downturns (Christie & Huang, 1995; Chang et al., 2000; Demirer & Kutan, 2006; Chiang & Zheng, 2010; Demirer et al., 2010; Yao et al., 2014; Filip et al., 2015).

Table 5. Asymmetric effects of returns on herd behavior.

Industries	α	γ_1	γ_2	γ_3	γ_4	Adj. R^2
All	0.012*** (0.000)	0.465*** (0.000)	0.472*** (0.000)	5.525*** (0.000)	-0.102 (0.809)	0.5153*** (0.000)
Industrials	0.010*** (0.000)	0.473*** (0.000)	0.474*** (0.000)	3.938*** (0.000)	-0.362 (0.329)	0.4890*** (0.000)
Technology	0.012*** (0.000)	0.434*** (0.000)	0.391*** (0.000)	-0.724 (0.623)	-0.894** (0.041)	0.3134*** (0.000)
Utilities	0.010*** (0.000)	0.441*** (0.000)	0.563*** (0.000)	11.904*** (0.000)	1.180 (0.127)	0.4040*** (0.000)
Basic Materials	0.011*** (0.000)	0.400*** (0.000)	0.349*** (0.000)	4.251*** (0.002)	2.439*** (0.000)	0.3932*** (0.000)
Financials	0.007*** (0.000)	0.620*** (0.000)	0.694*** (0.000)	3.104*** (0.005)	-2.020*** (0.000)	0.6052*** (0.000)
Consumer Good	0.012*** (0.000)	0.173*** (0.000)	0.329*** (0.000)	14.520*** (0.000)	1.862*** (0.001)	0.5705*** (0.000)
Health Care	0.015*** (0.000)	0.730*** (0.000)	0.545*** (0.000)	-0.494 (0.797)	1.625** (0.033)	0.4042*** (0.000)
Oil & Gas	0.013*** (0.000)	0.360*** (0.000)	0.363*** (0.000)	10.075*** (0.000)	4.030*** (0.000)	0.3533*** (0.000)
Consumer Services	0.009*** (0.0)	0.248*** (0.000)	0.425*** (0.000)	27.701*** (0.000)	1.963 (0.173)	0.3462*** (0.000)

Notes: ***, ** indicate significance at 1% and 5%, respectively. P-values are reported in parentheses.

The regression results of the equation (4) reported in **Table 6** reveal that, for the full-sample, the coefficient γ_3 is negative and statistically significant, indicating that herd behavior is present during periods of high trading volume. The result is consistent with the findings of previous studies, such as Galariotis et al. (2016), who reported evidence of herding during periods of high transaction volume in the French market. This finding differs from the ones reported by Mobarek et al. (2014) that did not document asymmetric herd behavior with reference to trading volume in French stock market for the period 2001-2012. Moreover, we notice that during periods of high trading volume, the coefficients γ_3 are negative and significant in the sectors of Industrials, Technology and Financials, suggesting that investors in these three sectors tend to act collectively in the same way. In the rest of the sectors, we point out the presence of an antihherding behavior. Consequently, H_{2b} is accepted in case of high trading volume. Our results confirm the studies of Litimi (2017) and BenSaïda (2017), who found that sectoral herding behavior is more responsive during periods of high transaction volume. However, our results contradict a study by Zheng et al. (2017) who reported evidence of herding during periods of low transaction volume.

Table 6. Asymmetric effects of trading volume on herd behavior.

Industries	α	γ_1	γ_2	γ_3	γ_4	Adj. R^2
All	0.012*** (0.000)	0.554*** (0.000)	0.322*** (0.000)	-0.818** (0.048)	6.558*** (0.042)	0.5115*** (0.000)
Industrials	0.010*** (0.000)	0.589*** (0.000)	0.301*** (0.000)	-1.184*** (0.001)	3.362 (0.196)	0.4949*** (0.000)
Technology	0.013*** (0.000)	0.444*** (0.000)	0.105 (0.111)	-1.663*** (0.000)	11.246*** (0.003)	0.3341*** (0.000)
Utilities	0.010*** (0.000)	0.684*** (0.000)	0.282*** (0.002)	-0.074 (0.923)	14.472*** (0.009)	0.4121*** (0.000)
Basic Materials	0.012*** (0.000)	0.427*** (0.000)	0.146** (0.026)	1.692*** (0.000)	9.731*** (0.000)	0.3974*** (0.000)
Financials	0.007*** (0.000)	0.727*** (0.000)	0.430*** (0.000)	-2.182*** (0.000)	13.328*** (0.003)	0.6077*** (0.000)
Consumer Goods	0.013*** (0.000)	0.417*** (0.000)	-0.063* (0.062)	0.997** (0.037)	23.309*** (0.000)	0.6349*** (0.000)
Health Care	0.015*** (0.000)	0.696*** (0.000)	0.161*** (0.010)	-1.034 (0.163)	17.446*** (0.000)	0.4303*** (0.000)
Oil & Gas	0.014*** (0.000)	0.552*** (0.000)	-0.007 (0.918)	1.492 (0.122)	19.242*** (0.000)	0.3743*** (0.000)
Consumer Services	0.009*** (0.000)	0.620*** (0.000)	0.181** (0.023)	-0.071 (0.961)	19.343*** (0.001)	0.3322*** (0.000)

Notes: ***, ** indicate significance at 1% and 5%, respectively. P-values are reported in parentheses.

The regression results of the equation 5 are reported in **Table 7**. The results show that the coefficient γ_4 of the full sample is negative and statistically significant, which indicates that herd behavior is present in periods of low volatility. At the industry level, the results reveal that the coefficients γ_3 and γ_4 are negative and statistically significant in the sectors of Industrials and Technology. This evidence suggests that herding behavior in these two sectors does not depend on the level of volatility. The presence of herding behavior during periods of high and low volatility supports the findings of previous studies of Tan et al. (2008), Economou et al. (2011), Mobarek et al. (2014), and Economou et al. (2016). In contrast, herding behavior is pronounced in the sector of utilities only in periods of low volatility since the coefficient γ_4 is negative and significant, while γ_3 is positive and non-significant. This finding of evidence for the herding effect under a low volatility condition supports the findings of (Holmes et al., 2013; Economou et al., 2015; Ukpong et al., 2021). For the financial sector, we document a negative and statistically significant coefficient γ_3 , indicating that this sector exhibits herding behavior during the period of high volatility. Gleason et al. (2004) suggest that herding behavior tends to intensify when market volatility is elevated, as investors seek guidance by aligning with the perceived consensus. This finding of the presence of herding behavior during periods of high volatility corroborates previous findings of (Tan et al., 2008; Gavriilidis et al., 2013). Therefore, H_{2c} is accepted in case of high and low volatility phases. The rest of sectors, particularly Basic Materials, Consumer Good, Oil & Gas and Consumer Services, the results are in favor of antiherding.

Table 7. Asymmetric effects of volatility on herd behavior.

Industries	α	γ_1	γ_2	γ_3	γ_4	Adj. R^2
All	0.011*** (0.000)	0.538*** (0.000)	0.821*** (0.000)	-0.350 (0.391)	-11.485*** (0.007)	0.5112*** (0.000)
Industrials	0.009*** (0.000)	0.567*** (0.000)	0.744*** (0.000)	-0.725** (0.043)	-12.528*** (0.000)	0.4809*** (0.000)
Technology	0.012*** (0.000)	0.433*** (0.000)	0.624*** (0.000)	-1.224*** (0.004)	-10.929*** (0.008)	0.3160*** (0.000)
Utilities	0.009*** (0.000)	0.660*** (0.000)	0.958*** (0.000)	0.763 (0.310)	-21.952*** (0.007)	0.3984*** (0.000)
Basic Materials	0.011*** (0.000)	0.377*** (0.000)	0.329*** (0.000)	2.429*** (0.000)	16.422*** (0.002)	0.3959*** (0.000)
Financials	0.006*** (0.000)	0.701*** (0.000)	0.944*** (0.000)	-1.637*** (0.000)	2.333 (0.735)	0.6152*** (0.000)
Consumer Goods	0.012*** (0.000)	0.312*** (0.000)	0.549*** (0.000)	5.503*** (0.000)	1.382 (0.757)	0.4821*** (0.000)
Health Care	0.014***	0.622***	0.678***	0.763	-0.131	0.3966***

	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.305)	(0.985)	(0.000)
Oil & Gas	0.012	0.399***	0.548***	5.495***	13.263*	0.3476***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.073)	(0.000)
Consumer Services	0.009***	0.513***	0.509***	3.289**	36.257**	0.3180***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.022)	(0.032)	(0.000)

Notes: ***, **, * indicate significance at 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively. P-values are reported in parentheses.

The empirical results for herding behavior during two different crisis events are reported in **Table 8**. Panel A results show that the coefficient γ_3 is negative and statistically significant in the sectors of Industrials, Technology, Utilities, Basic Materials and Health Care, suggesting that investors within these sectors were more inclined to align with overall market sentiment during the COVID-19 pandemic. Heightened fear and uncertainty regarding the pandemic's consequences led less informed investors to discard their own judgments and mimic the behavior of more informed participants (Espinosa-Méndez & Arias, 2021a). Panel B presents the findings related to the crisis triggered by the Russian invasion of Ukraine. The results show that the coefficients γ_3 are negative and statistically significant in the Health Care and Consumer Services sectors. This indicates that investors in these two sectors tend to flock together when they trade securities. Our evidence on the formation of herding behavior during crisis periods are consistent with previous findings of Mobarek et al. (2014), Wu et al. (2020), Espinosa-Méndez and Arias (2021a), Mishra and Mishra (2023), Ampofo et al. (2023), Bougateg and Nejah (2023), and Nguyen et al. (2023).

Table 8. Effects of crises on herd behavior.

Industries	α	γ_1	γ_2	γ_3	Adj. R^2
Panel A : Covid-19 Crisis					
All	0.012*** (0.000)	0.580*** (0.000)	-3.660*** (0.001)	2.824*** (0.002)	0.5042*** (0.000)
Industrials	0.010*** (0.000)	0.497*** (0.000)	1.726* (0.054)	-2.026*** (0.006)	0.4763*** (0.000)
Technology	0.012*** (0.000)	0.385*** (0.000)	0.352 (0.726)	-1.293* (0.099)	0.3131*** (0.000)
Utilities	0.010*** (0.000)	0.567*** (0.000)	4.372** (0.019)	-2.913** (0.048)	0.3965*** (0.000)
Basic Materials	0.011*** (0.000)	0.321*** (0.000)	5.938*** (0.000)	-4.476*** (0.000)	0.4143*** (0.000)
Financials	0.007***	0.747***	-4.011***	1.824**	0.5998***

	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.038)	(0.000)
Consumer Good	0.012***	0.315***	5.282***	0.666*	0.4757***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.057)	(0.000)
Health Care	0.015***	0.543***	4.800***	-4.296***	0.4057***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
Oil & Gas	0.013***	0.410***	5.884***	-1.260	0.3374***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.200)	(0.000)
Consumer Services	0.009***	0.508***	5.051*	-2.372	0.3097***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.072)	(0.269)	(0.000)

Panel B: Russia-Ukraine conflict

All	0.012***	0.519***	-0.325	2.000	0.5019***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.428)	(0.105)	(0.000)
Industrials	0.010***	0.540***	-0.572	-0.432	0.4736***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.113)	(0.751)	(0.000)
Technology	0.012***	0.414***	-1.133***	0.419	0.3119***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.007)	(0.713)	(0.000)
Utilities	0.010***	0.604***	1.120	3.608**	0.3967***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.132)	(0.033)	(0.000)
Basic Materials	0.011***	0.404***	2.070***	1.053	0.3872***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.327)	(0.000)
Financials	0.007***	0.712***	-1.900***	1.019	0.5988***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.451)	(0.000)
Consumer Good	0.012***	0.325***	5.204***	-0.576	0.4736***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.665)	(0.000)
Health Care	0.015***	0.639***	0.719	-2.996**	0.3987***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.324)	(0.025)	(0.000)
Oil & Gas	0.013***	0.418***	4.823***	2.807	0.3378***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.109)	(0.000)
Consumer Services	0.009***	0.562***	2.212	-6.485**	0.3112***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.119)	(0.037)	(0.000)

Notes: ***, **, * indicate significance at 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively. P-values are reported in parentheses.

The results of the regression of Equation (8) are reported in **Table 9**. The results demonstrates that, for the entire market, the coefficient γ_3 is negative and statistically significant, indicating the presence of herd behavior in periods of high uncertainty. Moreover, at the industry level, we document that the coefficient γ_3 is negative and statistically significant in the sectors of Industrials, Technology and Financials, which indicates that herd behavior is present in these sectors in periods of high

uncertainty. This evidence suggests that herd behavior in these sectors is driven by investor fear (Ghorbel et al. 2022). In times of market stress, when fear and panic prevail in the market, individual, retail or institutional investors may tend to employ a “flight to safety” strategy (Christie & Huang 1995; Economou et al., 2018; Aharon, 2021). Therefore, the hypothesis **H4** is accepted for 3 sectors out of 9. In contrast, the Consumer Goods sector exhibit an anti-herding behavior during high and low uncertainty.

Table 9. Impact of economic policy uncertainty on herding behavior.

Industries	α	γ_1	γ_2	γ_3	γ_4	Adj. R^2
All	0.012*** (0.000)	0.587*** (0.000)	0.199*** (0.000)	-1.262*** (0.002)	7.596*** (0.010)	0.5381*** (0.000)
Industrials	0.011*** (0.000)	0.522*** (0.000)	-0.001 (0.977)	-0.721** (0.039)	23.692*** (0.000)	0.5201*** (0.000)
Technology	0.013*** (0.000)	0.416*** (0.000)	0.103** (0.025)	-1.498*** (0.000)	12.071*** (0.000)	0.3395*** (0.000)
Utilities	0.010*** (0.000)	0.711*** (0.000)	0.304*** (0.000)	-0.344 (0.645)	8.319 (0.104)	0.4202*** (0.000)
Basic Materials	0.011*** (0.000)	0.473*** (0.000)	0.228*** (0.000)	-0.458 (0.335)	10.262*** (0.000)	0.4553*** (0.000)
Financials	0.007*** (0.000)	0.754*** (0.000)	0.360*** (0.000)	-2.524*** (0.000)	12.749** (0.026)	0.6186*** (0.000)
Consumer Goods	0.012*** (0.000)	0.369*** (0.000)	0.137** (0.023)	4.505*** (0.000)	8.364*** (0.003)	0.4847*** (0.000)
Health Care	0.016*** (0.000)	0.664*** (0.000)	0.079 (0.229)	-0.663 (0.365)	22.677*** (0.000)	0.4347*** (0.000)
Oil and Gas	0.014*** (0.000)	0.519*** (0.000)	-0.045 (0.484)	1.593 (0.096)	23.171*** (0.000)	0.3845*** (0.000)
Consumer Services	0.009*** (0.000)	0.578*** (0.000)	0.204*** (0.005)	0.585 (0.686)	22.037*** (0.000)	0.3243*** (0.000)

Notes: ***, **, * indicate significance at 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively. P-values are reported in parentheses.

4.2. Results of Quantile Regressions

Following Chiang et al. (2010) and Pochea et al. (2017), the quantiles are determined at 10%, 25%, 50%, 75% and 90%. **Table 10** shows the regression results of Equations (8), (9), (10), (11), (12) and (13) with QR estimates. The results of Eq. 8 show that the herding coefficient is negative and significant in the quantiles from low to medium levels ($\tau = 10\%$ - 50%) for the Technology sector and from medium to high quantiles ($\tau = 50\%$ - 90%) for the Financial sector. This means that the Technology

and the Financial sectors exhibit herding behavior for the entire sample period. Similar results are obtained using the OLS approach. Looking at the results of Eq. 9 for the bearish and bullish markets, it appears that the herding behavior is more pronounced under bearish market conditions for the Technology and the Financial sectors. This strong herding tendency in bear markets can be explained by a flight-to-quality phenomenon. Indeed, in reaction to series of consecutive losses and periods of volatility on the markets, risk aversion tends to increase, resulting in a flight to quality, as shown by Gebka and Wohar (2013). According to the results of Eq. 10, we notice that herding behavior is present in the entire market, as well as at the sector level during periods of high trading volume in different quantile levels. In fact, the coefficients are negative and significant in low quantiles for the Basic Materials ($\tau = 25\%$), Financials ($\tau = 10\%$, 25% and 50%) and Health Care ($\tau = 25\%$) sectors. In contrast, the coefficient is negative and significant in high quantiles for the Technology sector ($\tau = 75\%$ and 90%). The estimated results of Eq. 11 show that the herding coefficient $\gamma_{4,\tau}$ for the entire market is negative and significant in the high quantile during periods of low volatility. Likewise, at the sector level, we note strong herding behavior during periods of low volatility, since the herding coefficient $\gamma_{4,\tau}$ is negative and significant in all quantiles for the Industrial sector and in low quantiles for the Technology and Utilities sectors. For the Financial sector, the coefficient $\gamma_{3,\tau}$ is negative and significant in the low quantile ($\tau = 10\%$), which indicates the presence of herding behavior during periods of high volatility. Similar to previous studies (such as Tan et al., 2008; Lakshman et al., 2013), high volatility is one of the most important determinants of herding behavior due to increased uncertainty and fear of losses, leading investors to follow others and imitating group behaviors. The results of Eq. 12 indicate that only the Utilities and Health Care sectors are affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, since the herding coefficient $\gamma_{3^{covid},\tau}^{19}$ is negative and significant in low quantiles for both sectors.

Table 10. Results of Herding Equations (8), (9), (10), (11), (12) & (13).**Table 10.** Results of Herding Equations (8), (9), (10), (11), (12) & (13).

Sector	Quantile	Eq. 8		Eq. 9		Eq. 10		Eq. 11		Eq. 12		Eq. 13	
		$\gamma_{2,r}$	$\gamma_{3,r}$	$\gamma_{4,r}$	$\gamma_{3,r}$	$\gamma_{4,r}$	$\gamma_{3,r}$	$\gamma_{4,r}$	$\gamma_{3,r}$	$\gamma_{4,r}$	$\gamma_{3covid,r}$	$\gamma_{3war,r}$	$\gamma_{3,r}$
All	$\tau=0.10$	0.396	7.904***	0.510	0.323	5.853***	0.256	2.391	6.101*	5.875***	-0.054	3.577	
		(0.152)	(0.000)	(0.102)	(0.309)	(0.000)	(0.3699)	(0.328)	(0.087)	(0.000)	(0.873)	(0.619)	
	$\tau=0.25$	-0.254	5.500***	0.117	-0.371	3.403**	-0.173	-2.188	2.419	4.971***	-0.767***	5.620***	
		(0.276)	(0.000)	(0.656)	(0.144)	(0.016)	(0.523)	(0.385)	(0.315)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	
	$\tau=0.5$	0.104	8.462	-0.012	-0.766***	11.173	1.557	-4.176	4.044***	3.826***	-1.330***	8.724	
		(0.987)	(0.190)	(0.991)	(0.007)	(0.221)	(0.853)	(0.275)	(0.003)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.018)	
	$\tau=0.75$	1.602***	8.646***	2.544***	1.090*	11.157***	1.866	-8.687**	2.645**	0.822	0.616	12.104	
		(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.062)	(0.000)	(0.684)	(0.039)	(0.034)	(0.595)	(0.275)	(0.332)	
	$\tau=0.90$	-0.215	16.856***	0.466	-0.931	11.090	6.713	9.988	12.475***	-3.314	-2.793	14.684	
		(0.720)	(0.000)	(0.425)	(0.377)	(0.330)	(0.866)	(0.875)	(0.005)	(0.864)	(0.128)	(0.203)	
Industrials	$\tau=0.10$	0.497***	5.253***	0.767***	0.355**	4.482***	0.411**	-4.361***	2.271	4.064**	0.259*	2.109	
		(0.003)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.048)	(0.001)	(0.023)	(0.001)	(0.586)	(0.013)	(0.090)	(0.121)	
	$\tau=0.25$	0.216	4.995***	0.566***	-0.217	2.317	0.009	-6.143***	1.662	3.962***	-0.328	-0.344	
		(0.299)	(0.000)	(0.002)	(0.353)	(0.135)	(0.971)	(0.000)	(0.386)	(0.000)	(0.135)	(0.833)	
	$\tau=0.5$	0.735**	4.607***	1.541***	0.317	4.311	0.877***	-5.305***	3.333	3.810***	0.236	1.650	
		(0.013)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.323)	(0.610)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.156)	(0.000)	(0.368)	(0.458)	
	$\tau=0.75$	3.012	7.902	0.319	-0.860	6.681***	3.342**	-6.053***	2.872	0.043	0.933	32.503	
		(0.567)	(0.383)	(0.350)	(0.789)	(0.000)	(0.013)	(0.000)	(0.594)	(0.991)	(0.821)	(0.276)	
	$\tau=0.90$	17.784**	26.142	3.799	11.162	17.663	16.996**	-13.236***	12.045***	-8.436*	-2.013	43.831***	

		(0.004)	(0.387)	(0.198)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.001)	(0.005)	(0.991)	(0.064)	(0.000)	(0.311)
	$\tau=0.75$	-2.009***	-1.496*	-1.371***	-2.292***	10.277	-2.092***	-9.352***	1.523*	1.291	-2.054***	13.123
		(0.000)	(0.091)	(0.001)	(0.000)	(0.332)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.076)	(0.226)	(0.000)	(0.673)
	$\tau=0.90$	-2.785***	5.768*	-2.663***	-2.799***	30.830***	-2.678***	-13.599***	1.317	-1.059	-2.606***	24.218***
		(0.000)	(0.080)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.187)	(0.263)	(0.000)	(0.000)
Utilities	$\tau=0.10$	1.226*	9.390***	1.761**	0.384	-0.710	0.553	-14.033***	-8.310***	7.288***	-0.087	-6.709
		(0.079)	(0.000)	(0.018)	(0.660)	(0.915)	(0.453)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.922)	(0.157)
	$\tau=0.25$	3.468***	12.934	2.954	2.979***	13.300	3.322***	-18.431***	-3.797**	3.006***	2.831***	2.080
		(0.000)	(0.246)	(0.958)	(0.000)	(0.313)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.016)	(0.002)	(0.000)	(0.718)
	$\tau=0.5$	1.469***	11.597*	2.519***	0.946	21.100***	1.413**	-7.518	-4.486	6.307***	0.662	13.165**
		(0.001)	(0.074)	(0.000)	(0.118)	(0.001)	(0.023)	(0.883)	(0.506)	(0.001)	(0.346)	(0.016)
	$\tau=0.75$	7.827	10.307**	1.471	2.566	40.163***	8.559	9.790	-0.976	9.090	0.752	20.671*
		(0.493)	(0.024)	(0.922)	(0.877)	(0.001)	(0.515)	(0.913)	(0.891)	(0.176)	(0.958)	(0.077)
	$\tau=0.90$	14.901	18.874***	6.832	3.743	56.449***	20.777**	86.954	12.299***	9.481	1.997	29.940*
		(0.754)	(0.000)	(0.338)	(0.641)	(0.000)	(0.039)	(0.149)	(0.003)	(0.657)	(0.781)	(0.064)
Basic Materials	$\tau=0.10$	-0.002	2.867***	0.499**	-0.099	3.721	0.134	3.670**	-0.233	-0.194	0.280	11.785***
		(0.992)	(0.000)	(0.045)	(0.638)	(0.413)	(0.540)	(0.044)	(0.883)	(0.666)	(0.214)	(0.000)
	$\tau=0.25$	1.031	1.846***	0.058	-0.539**	5.142***	2.005	5.717	-0.022	1.088	-0.304	11.499***
		(0.888)	(0.003)	(0.801)	(0.020)	(0.000)	(0.822)	(0.856)	(0.996)	(0.861)	(0.197)	(0.000)
	$\tau=0.5$	3.003***	5.001**	4.127***	2.857***	11.474***	3.504***	24.269***	-0.719	2.743	0.898	10.779***
	(0.000)	(0.013)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.004)	(0.876)	(0.319)	(0.952)	(0.000)	
	$\tau=0.75$	8.253	7.245*	7.350	5.726	23.040***	9.840***	37.116***	-1.939	2.712	0.938	9.443***
		(0.315)	(0.081)	(0.774)	(0.812)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.747)	(0.445)	(0.141)	(0.000)
	$\tau=0.90$	8.209***	16.982	8.961***	8.129***	21.065*	9.318	43.366***	1.136	3.995***	4.354	24.929***
		(0.000)	(0.613)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.071)	(0.168)	(0.000)	(0.967)	(0.000)	(0.587)	(0.000)
Financials	$\tau=0.10$	-0.527*	5.645***	-0.434	-0.695**	14.865**	-0.551*	4.257	-1.358	4.978***	-0.737***	7.646
		(0.058)	(0.000)	(0.118)	(0.019)	(0.053)	(0.080)	(0.208)	(0.549)	(0.000)	(0.011)	(0.139)
	$\tau=0.25$	-1.340***	4.280***	-1.202***	-1.504***	13.369***	-1.303***	-6.759**	-0.583	3.490***	-1.571***	9.847
		(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.003)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.050)	(0.908)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.265)

	$\tau=0.5$	-1.667*** (0.000)	3.756*** (0.000)	-1.553*** (0.001)	-1.857*** (0.000)	9.615*** (0.000)	-1.066 (0.892)	-6.207 (0.614)	1.765 (0.647)	2.429 (0.214)	-2.201*** (0.000)	4.802 (0.195)
	$\tau=0.75$	-0.383 (0.844)	4.988 (0.1479)	-2.320*** (0.000)	-1.071 (0.373)	19.600 (0.592)	0.326 (0.875)	8.788 (0.767)	4.214 (0.184)	-1.855 (0.246)	-2.724 (0.115)	22.245** (0.024)
	$\tau=0.90$	-1.759 (0.388)	9.502 (0.322)	-2.892 (0.102)	-2.623 (0.340)	33.661** (0.032)	2.685 (0.831)	74.061 (0.749)	5.494 (0.598)	-0.263 (0.735)	-3.468 (0.169)	30.364*** (0.003)
Consumer Goods	$\tau=0.10$	1.628*** (0.000)	4.146*** (0.000)	2.535*** (0.000)	0.780* (0.083)	4.398 (0.302)	1.838*** (0.000)	4.510 (0.172)	0.665*** (0.000)	3.495*** (0.000)	1.024** (0.027)	2.742*** (0.007)
	$\tau=0.25$	1.837*** (0.000)	5.983*** (0.000)	2.178*** (0.000)	1.477*** (0.000)	10.751 (0.198)	1.964*** (0.000)	1.010 (0.601)	0.436** (0.018)	2.217*** (0.008)	1.133*** (0.000)	1.516 (0.156)
	$\tau=0.5$	1.933 (0.293)	5.276 (0.501)	1.746*** (0.000)	1.070*** (0.001)	23.773*** (0.000)	2.994 (0.249)	-0.500 (0.836)	0.429*** (0.006)	1.688 (0.548)	1.371 (0.469)	7.795 (0.218)
	$\tau=0.75$	5.713*** (0.000)	21.187*** (0.000)	3.528*** (0.000)	2.824*** (0.003)	23.896*** (0.000)	6.271*** (0.000)	14.570 (0.909)	1.581 (0.647)	-0.813 (0.256)	4.843*** (0.000)	21.023*** (0.002)
	$\tau=0.90$	21.355*** (0.000)	19.446 (0.000)	0.764 (0.394)	0.562 (0.738)	22.554*** (0.000)	23.273*** (0.000)	49.360*** (0.004)	7.181* (0.081)	-8.944*** (0.002)	15.655 (0.793)	22.870** (0.023)
	Health Care	$\tau=0.10$	-0.440 (0.253)	0.028 (0.971)	0.437 (0.229)	-0.076 (0.894)	8.889 (0.484)	0.081 (0.830)	17.733*** (0.000)	-1.801*** (0.004)	1.706*** (0.000)	-0.936*** (0.009)
$\tau=0.25$		-0.253 (0.870)	3.153 (0.460)	-0.614 (0.129)	-1.223*** (0.008)	17.272*** (0.000)	0.100 (0.948)	7.495* (0.069)	-1.029 (0.223)	1.433 (0.131)	-1.395*** (0.001)	20.513*** (0.000)
$\tau=0.5$		8.048*** (0.001)	7.635** (0.037)	10.324*** (0.000)	-2.111 (0.889)	13.478*** (0.000)	8.450*** (0.000)	4.187 (0.581)	3.476 (0.412)	-1.464 (0.484)	0.181 (0.990)	26.493*** (0.000)
$\tau=0.75$		13.842 (0.187)	11.024** (0.025)	10.772 (0.783)	4.11** (0.046)	24.933*** (0.000)	14.269 (0.115)	6.927 (0.693)	1.969 (0.866)	-5.727 (0.388)	5.170** (0.022)	31.675*** (0.000)
$\tau=0.90$		14.780*** (0.000)	14.169** (0.066)	17.976*** (0.000)	11.966*** (0.000)	20.700*** (0.001)	15.209*** (0.000)	20.452 (0.101)	1.194 (0.885)	-7.273 (0.460)	13.415*** (0.000)	30.145*** (0.000)
Oil & Gas	$\tau=0.10$	3.337*** (0.003)	2.348** (0.014)	5.450 (0.102)	1.678 (0.145)	-0.368 (0.860)	3.624*** (0.001)	12.161*** (0.000)	5.405*** (0.000)	6.170*** (0.000)	3.486*** (0.008)	12.635 (0.223)
	$\tau=0.25$	3.302***	2.749	5.009***	2.553**	8.262	4.168***	21.103***	2.280***	3.702***	1.568	16.549**

	$\tau=0.5$	(0.001)	(0.737)	(0.000)	(0.023)	(0.419)	(0.000)	(0.005)	(0.008)	(0.001)	(0.772)	(0.019)
		2.366***	10.574	3.644***	1.160	25.357***	5.119	11.773	3.006	2.445	0.920	24.728***
		(0.009)	(0.104)	(0.000)	(0.227)	(0.000)	(0.557)	(0.219)	(0.221)	(0.513)	(0.899)	(0.000)
	$\tau=0.75$	5.030	17.855*	5.521***	2.254**	22.088***	7.891*	18.091	-2.056	4.267*	3.075***	21.881***
		(0.651)	(0.087)	(0.000)	(0.033)	(0.000)	(0.073)	(0.725)	(0.191)	(0.071)	(0.002)	(0.009)
	$\tau=0.90$	12.162	14.243***	1.773	-1.104	20.872***	18.064***	42.204*	-8.533	7.264	-0.606	32.437**
		(0.797)	(0.000)	(0.134)	(0.381)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.082)	(0.593)	(0.636)	(0.650)	(0.049)
Consumer Services	$\tau=0.10$	3.844***	12.053	5.122***	3.417***	3.875	3.794***	8.093	-3.324	-1.126	3.421***	2.036
		(0.000)	(0.365)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.119)	(0.000)	(0.595)	(0.290)	(0.914)	(0.000)	(0.439)
	$\tau=0.25$	3.079***	13.542***	4.051***	3.219***	32.424	3.315***	26.628***	-2.920	-0.434	3.130***	16.995***
		(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.123)	(0.000)	(0.004)	(0.462)	(0.814)	(0.000)	(0.000)
	$\tau=0.5$	8.749	35.526***	5.127	3.053	41.716***	9.410	21.293	-0.867	-6.671**	2.272*	20.044
		(0.411)	(0.000)	(0.204)	(0.469)	(0.000)	(0.348)	(0.327)	(0.878)	(0.023)	(0.067)	(0.417)
$\tau=0.75$	18.706	43.827**	1.541	6.345	50.948***	25.166	112.407***	-3.113	-17.381***	2.669	47.862**	
	(0.175)	(0.017)	(0.110)	(0.797)	(0.000)	(0.147)	(0.000)	(0.630)	(0.003)	(0.937)	(0.016)	
$\tau=0.90$	32.020	54.506***	-2.644	4.644	46.848***	50.449	133.501	12.272**	-9.324	19.380	61.803***	
	(0.448)	(0.000)	(0.103)	(0.794)	(0.000)	(0.111)	(0.405)	(0.058)	(0.519)	(0.709)	(0.000)	

Notes: ***, **, * indicate significance at 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively. P-values are reported in parentheses.

Source : Authors' Contribution.

Furthermore, the results of the crisis caused by the Russian invasion of Ukraine show that the herding coefficient $\gamma_{3^{war},\tau}$ is negative and significant in the high quantile ($\tau = 90\%$) for the Industrial, Consumer Goods and from medium to high quantiles ($\tau = 50\%-75\%$) for the Consumer Services sector. The estimation results of Eq. 13 reveal that herding behavior is present during periods of high economic uncertainty in the entire market in the lower quantiles ($\tau = 25\%$ and 50%), as well as in the Financial ($\tau = 10\%$, 25% and 50%) and Health Care ($\tau = 10\%$) sectors. For the Technological sector, we document strong herding behavior since the coefficient $\gamma_{3,\tau}$ is negative and significant in all quantiles except the quantile ($\tau = 10\%$).

4.3. Comparative Analysis : CSAD versus QR

Table 11 provides a comparative summary of the key findings obtained from the CSAD and QR models.

Table 11. The main results of the CSAD and QR models.

	CSAD Model	QR Approach
Herding behavior over the entire sample period	Absence of any herd effect on the French market. Presence of herd behavior in the sectors of Technology and Financials.	Herding behavior varies across quantiles. Technology and Financial sectors exhibit herding behavior for the entire sample period.
Bullish and bearish markets	Herding behavior on the entire French market does not depend on market return movements. Investors in the Technology and Financials sectors are more sensitive to loss during bearish market than to gain during bullish market. Herding behavior is more pronounced during market downturns.	Herding behavior is more pronounced under bearish market conditions for the Technology and the Financial sectors.
High and low trading volume	Herd behavior is present during periods of high trading volume.	Herding behavior is present in the entire market, as well as at the sector level during periods of high trading volume in different quantile levels.
High and low volatility	Herd behavior is present in periods of low volatility.	At the sector level, there is a strong herding behavior during periods of low volatility for the Industrial sector and in low quantiles for the Technology and Utilities sectors. For the Financial sector, we note a presence of herding behavior during periods of high volatility.

Herd behavior during crisis periods	Herding behavior is present during crisis periods	Only the Utilities and Health Care sectors are affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. The results of the crisis caused by the Russian invasion of Ukraine show a presence of herding behavior for the Industrial, Consumer Goods, and Consumer Services sector.
Herding behavior and EPU	Herding behavior is present in periods of high uncertainty.	Herding behavior is present during periods of high economic uncertainty in the entire, as well as in the Financial and Health Care sectors. For the Technological sector, we document strong herding behavior.

Source : Authors' Contribution.

Overall, both approaches identify evidence of herding behavior in the French stock market, but they differ in the level of detail and sensitivity to market conditions. The CSAD model offers a general view by focusing on average dispersion across the market. It does not detect herding over the full sample but identifies sector-specific effects, particularly in the Technology and Financial sectors. In contrast, the QR approach uncovers a more nuanced dynamic by capturing herding behavior across different market quantiles, confirming the presence of herding not only at the sectoral level but also across the entire market under specific conditions. When analyzing bullish and bearish market states, the CSAD model suggests that herding behavior is not significantly influenced by market direction at the aggregate level, although investors in Technology and Financials sectors show stronger reactions during downturns. The QR model supports this view and further highlights that herding is more intense in bearish conditions, consistent with the idea that uncertainty and fear amplify mimetic behavior. Regarding trading volume, both methods agree that herding intensifies during periods of high market activity, with the QR model providing deeper insight into how this effect varies across quantiles and sectors. In terms of market volatility, the CSAD model reveals herding primarily during low volatility periods. The QR model refines this finding by showing that while some sectors (like Industrial and Utilities) exhibit herding under low volatility, others (notably the Financial sector) do so in high-volatility contexts, illustrating sectoral heterogeneity. During crisis periods, both approaches confirm the presence of herding, though with different emphases. The CSAD model reports generalized herding during crises, whereas the QR model identifies sector-specific herding. Finally, under EPU, both models show that herding increases when uncertainty is high. However, the QR approach gives a more granular picture by highlighting the sectors most impacted - particularly Technology, Financials, and

Health Care - thus reinforcing its value in capturing conditional effects. Then, while the CSAD model is useful for detecting aggregate patterns, the QR approach offers a richer and more detailed understanding of herding behavior, especially under extreme market conditions and within specific sectors.

5. Robustness Test

In order to check the robustness of our results and to strengthen the reliability of our study, we adopt GARCH model, following the methodology used by Le et al. (2024) and Sharma et al. (2024). The results of the GARCH analysis to assess herd behavior are presented in Table 12. The results show that the coefficient of the quadratic term of market returns $R_{m,t}^2$ is positive and statistically significant at the 1% level, revealing anti-herding behavior on the part of investors, both at the level of the overall market and across all the sectors analyzed. This outcome aligns with our principal findings. Furthermore, the GARCH effect is positive and statistically significant in the conditional variance equation for all sectors, confirming the presence of volatility clustering in the stock return series for these sectors.

Table 12. Results of GARCH (1,1) Model Estimation.

	Conditional Mean Equations			Conditional Variance Equations		
	Constant	$ R_{m,t} $	$R_{m,t}^2$	Constant	ARCH	GARCH
ALL	0.012045*** (0,0000)	0.241999*** (0,0000)	4.338926*** (0,0000)	6.86E-07*** (0,0000)	0.457878*** (0,0000)	0.518448*** (0,0000)
Industrials	0.009844*** (0,0000)	0.266996*** (0,0000)	3.461223*** (0,0000)	4.46E-06*** (0,0000)	0.859190*** (0,0000)	0.140916*** (0,0000)
Technology	0.012359*** (0,0000)	0.373019*** (0,0000)	0.516323*** (0,0065)	6.89E-06*** (0,0000)	0.281875*** (0,0000)	0.337417*** (0,0000)
Utilities	0.009617*** (0,0000)	0.392281*** (0,0000)	8.437378*** (0,0000)	1.57E-06*** (0,0000)	0.132659*** (0,0000)	0.814938*** (0,0000)
Basic Materials	0.010982*** (0,0000)	0.173863*** (0,0000)	8.739912*** (0,0000)	8.79E-07*** (0,0000)	0.080311*** (0,0000)	0.904854*** (0,0000)
Financials	0.006621*** (0,0000)	0.553326*** (0,0000)	0.903847*** (0,0013)	1.75E-07*** (0,0000)	0.099869*** (0,0000)	0.879272*** (0,0000)
Consumer Goods	0.012462*** (0,0000)	0.035811* (0,0511)	10.12567*** (0,0000)	1.20E-06*** (0,0000)	0.485224*** (0,0000)	0.606690*** (0,0000)
Health Care	0.015390*** (0,0000)	0.252523*** (0,0000)	14.16095*** (0,0000)	4.76E-06*** (0,0000)	0.219252*** (0,0000)	0.684732*** (0,0000)
Oil & Gas	0.012501*** (0,0000)	0.262553*** (0,0000)	10.72809*** (0,0000)	2.01E-06*** (0,0000)	0.067755*** (0,0000)	0.905244*** (0,0000)
Consumer Services	0.009191*** (0,0000)	0.357938*** (0,0000)	9.348842*** (0,0000)	6.97E-06*** (0,0000)	0.180404*** (0,0000)	0.390671*** (0,0000)

Notes: ***, **, * indicate significance at 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively. P-values are reported in parentheses

Source : Authors' Contribution.

6. Conclusion

The present paper examined the presence of herding behavior in the French stock market. Unlike the majority of previous studies who attempted to detect herding behavior in global stock market, this study investigated this behavior at the industry level. Applying the CSAD approach of Chang et al. (2000) and the Quantile approach on daily data of 270 companies listed on Euronext Paris, our goal was to capture herding behavior in seven activity sectors under different market conditions and during two crisis periods. We assessed the asymmetric effects of returns, trading volume and volatility on herding behavior. In addition, we investigated the relationship between the economic policy uncertainty (EPU) and the formation of herding behavior. Moreover, the hypothesis of the occurrence of herding behavior during crisis periods such as the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak and the Russia-Ukraine war was tested. Our findings reveal that herding behavior is present only in some sectors. In addition, some market conditions such as downturn, volatility and trading volume turn out to contribute significantly to the formation of herding behavior. Moreover, investors in some sectors tend to herd during crisis periods, namely the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak and the Russia-Ukraine war, and when the level of uncertainty is high. The comparative analysis of the key findings obtained from the CSAD and QR models shows that, while the CSAD model is useful for detecting aggregate patterns, the QR approach offers a richer and more detailed understanding of herding behavior, especially under extreme market conditions and within specific sectors.

Implications : The empirical results of this study are worthwhile for all market participants since they help to understand the causes of abnormal returns in some sectors. The presence of herding in the Technology and Financials sectors implies that policymakers should remove information asymmetry in these two sectors to avoid mispricing and ensure market efficiency. The anti-herding behavior documented in the sectors of Basic materials, Consumer goods and Oil & Gas may be attributed to a good information environment in these sectors. The presence of herding in some sectors and anti-herding in others imply that investors and portfolio managers should diversify their investment across different sectors to limit loss resulting from herding.

Limitations and future line of research: This study presents two limitations. First, it is limited to the French stock market due to the absence of previous studies on the effects of COVID-19 and the Russia-Ukraine war on sectoral herding. Future researches on sectoral herding could conduct a comparative study between developed and emerging markets since it is argued that herding behavior depends on the degree of stock market development. Second,

in this study, we apply the OLS and the quantile regressions to capture herding behavior, while time-varying analysis such as rolling-window regression could be more appropriate to detect this behavior.

Submission Declaration Statement:

We hereby confirm that the manuscript has no actual or potential conflict of interest with any parties, including any financial, personal, or other relationships with other people or organizations within three years of beginning the submitted work that could inappropriately influence or be perceived to influence. We confirm that the paper has not been published previously, it is not under consideration for publication elsewhere, and the manuscript is not being simultaneously submitted elsewhere.

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